

Association between photoperiod sensitivity and basic vegetative growth phase of rice

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Vegetative growth of rice plants can be divided into basic and photoperiod-sensitive, two phases considered to be independently inherited. But experiments with isogenic lines show an association.

A series of alleles at the *Lm* locus, which belongs to the linkage group I, largely controls variation in heading time of cultivated rices. To obtain isogenic lines, individuals heterozygous at the *Lm* locus were selected during 15 generations (from F₁ through BC₄F₁₁) of a cross between Malaysian cultivar Morak Sepilai and Japanese cultivar Fujisaka 5. Fujisaka 5 was used as the recurrent parent through four successive backcrosses. Morak Sepilai transmitted the late-maturing allele *Lm^u* and Fujisaka 5 the early-maturing allele *Lm^e* to the hybrid progeny.

The BC₄F₁₀ population derived from a single medium-maturing BC₄F₉ plant showed a trimodal distribution for heading time in agreement with the segregation ratio of 1:2:1. This suggests that heading time is controlled by one gene (Fig. 1). Genotypes for three classes of heading time were homozygous early *Lm^e / Lm^e*, heterozygous medium *Lm^e / Lm^u*, and homozygous late *Lm^u / Lm^u*.

1. Heading time of 238 UC₄F₁₀ plants under natural day length conditions, Japan.

Two early and two late homozygous BC₄F₁₂ lines were tested for heading time in 8- and 15-hour photoperiod treatments. Plants were placed under natural daylight from 9 am to 5 pm. In the 8-hour-photoperiod treatment, plants were kept in complete darkness for 16 hours. In the 15-hour-photoperiod treatment, plant illumination by fluorescent lamps for an additional 7 hours was followed by 9 hours of darkness. The light intensity was 720 lux on the plant-leaf level.

Under the short-day condition, *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants headed 44 days after sowing (DS) and *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants headed 60 DS (Fig. 2). The long-day treatment markedly delayed heading in both genotypes. *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants headed 93 DS. *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants did not reach heading within 130 days, indicating that *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants are more sensitive to photoperiod than *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants.

Assuming that the two phases of vegetative growth period are controlled by different genes, under short-day conditions, *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants should have the same vegetative growth period as *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants, since they are nearly isogenic in photoperiod sensitivity. But in this study, short-day treatment accel-

2. Effect of 2 photoperiod treatments on days to heading of 2 isogenic lines with *Lm^e* and *Lm^u*, Japan. Lines that did not head within 130 days were considered nonheading.

erated heading of *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants more than it did that of *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants. This indicates that the basic vegetative phase is influenced to some extent by photoperiod-sensitive genes. A short basic vegetative phase appears to be associated with photoperiod sensitivity. ■

Rice seedling growth and metabolism in response to penicillin

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Penicillin promoted the elongation of rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. Jaya) seedlings almost linearly, depending upon concentration. The promotion of shoot elongation was stronger (40% over control)

than that of root elongation (25% over control). Nucleic acids and protein contents were maintained at higher levels, with a more pronounced effect in embryo than in endosperm (see table). In the embryo, DNA was 88%, RNA was 90%, and protein was 40% more than control at 1,000 ppm. Endosperm DNA and RNA followed the same pattern, measuring about 35% over control at 1,000 ppm. Protein content exceeded that in the control by 30% at 500 ppm. This suggests that the growth-promoting

effect of penicillin is mediated through its influence on nucleic and protein synthesis.

Penicillin stimulated the activity of both ribonuclease and α -amylase (see table). The highest activity of RNase was recorded at 500 ppm (5 times control) and that of α -amylase at 1,000 ppm (35% above control).

Penicillin in the presence and absence of GA₃ was shown to influence elongation of the second leaf sheath of TN1 rice seedlings (see figure). Sensitivity of

Effect of penicillin on nucleic acid^a and protein content^b and enzyme activity of rice seedlings. Calcutta, India.

Treatment	Embryo of 5-day-old seedlings			Endosperm (3 days after germination)				
	DNA	RNA	Protein	DNA	RNA	Protein	α -amylase ^c	RNase ^d
Control	16	58	3.5	23	91	3.1	3.4	0.40
Penicillin (ppm)								
500	25	101	4.5	33	127	4.0	4.6	1.96
1,000	30	110	4.9	31	122	3.5	4.6	1.30

^aDNA and RNA are in $\mu\text{g}/100$ mg fresh wt. ^bProtein is in $\text{mg}/100$ mg fresh wt. ^cAs mg maltose released per 10 endosperms and 10 minutes. ^dAbsorbancy at 260 nm per 10 endosperms and 30 minutes.

seedlings increased progressively when GA₃ was combined with increasing concentrations of penicillin. The interaction

was additive. Penicillin probably stimulated elongation in a manner similar to GA₃. ■

Elongation of second leaf sheath of TN1 rice seedlings. 1 = control (water); 2, 3, 4 = 100, 500, and 1,000 ppm penicillin, respectively; 5 = GA₃ (10^{-5} M); 6 = GA₃ + 100 ppm penicillin; 7 = GA₃ + 500 ppm penicillin; 8 = GA₃ + 1,000 ppm penicillin.

Aeroponic technique for root system studies of rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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In studies of the relationship of rice root systems to drought resistance at IRRI since 1970, roots have been grown in soil-filled mylar tubes, root boxes, and in the field. These methods and attendant sampling problems are laborious and time-consuming, and damage to roots can occur during sampling of large populations. The need to study a rice root system with its components intact led to the development of an aeroponic culture system. A nutrient solution is pumped from a reservoir through an atomizing mist nozzle at the base of a cylindrical drum (see figure) about 90 cm in diameter. The nutrient solution mist continuously bathes rice roots hanging from the cylinder top. Excess nutrient solution drains back into the reservoir for reuse. The cylinder is covered with a plywood top in which plants are grown in Styrofoam plant holders. Holes 5.0 cm in diameter spaced 7.5 cm centers allow the plants to grow competitively without entangling their roots. Each plant holder is 5.0 cm in diameter with a 2.1 cm center hole. The bottom of each holder is wrapped with plastic screen held securely by a rubber band.

To produce good quality seedlings for

General view of the aeroponic device inside a phytotron glasshouse at IRRI.

use in the aeroponic system, rice seeds were pretreated with 0.2% mercuric chloride to prevent fungus growth and Pregerminated in petri dishes. After two days they were transferred to plastic sieves in a plastic tray containing just enough 50% concentration nutrient solution to cover the germinating seeds. After 11 days, seedlings were transplanted into Styrofoam plant holders inside the phytotron working area. Roots were sprayed with demineralized water to prevent dehydration during transplanting.

Immediately after seedlings were transferred to the drum cover, it was set on top of the drum, the aeroponic system switched on, and the seedlings

began to receive a mist of standard nutrient solution. The pH was adjusted to 5.0 before the solution was added to the aeroponic reservoir and readjusted daily to avoid nutrient imbalance. The culture solution was renewed weekly from transplanting to sampling.

During the first week after transplanting, only a 50% concentration of the prepared culture solution was used. Beginning from the second week, a full concentration was used. Nitrogen was increased from 40 to 80 ppm the fourth week.

Aeroponic chambers can be operated in a series by extending the air and nutrient solution pressure systems serving the units. ■